

AN X-RAY INVESTIGATION OF THE CRYSTALS OF DIPHENYLENE DISULPHIDE (THIANTHRENE) AND DIPHENYL DISULPHIDE

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The structure of several crystals of the aromatic compounds containing more than one benzene ring has been recently completely determined and the interatomic distances in many cases are now uniquely known. These substances may broadly be classed into two groups, one in which the rings are fused along a side and the other in which they are either joined end to end or joined through atoms or groups. Of the former the crystal of anthracene (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1930, **4**, 557; *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1933, **A 140**, 79) affords an important example, while the crystals of diphenyl and dibenzyl series (Dhar, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1932, **7**, 43; Pickett, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1934, **A 142**, 333; *Nature*, 1933, **131**, 153; Robertson, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1934, **A 140**, 473; and Robertson, Prasad and Woodward, *ibid.*, 1935, **A 151**, 187) belong to the latter type.

A study of the crystals of thianthrene and diphenyl disulphide was taken up with a view to find out if any relationship exists between these on the one hand and anthracene, and stilbene and azobenzene, respectively, on the other. In the present investigation only the space groups have been determined by the rotating and oscillating single crystal method using a monochromatic X-ray beam ($\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$).

Thianthrene.

Pure thianthrene* was further purified by recrystallisation from carbon disulphide from which well developed crystals were obtained by slow evaporation. When viewed through transmitted light, the crystals as well as the solution show a band of beautiful colours indicating their large dispersive power. The melting point of the crystals was found to be 154° and the specific gravity, determined by the flotation method, 1.442. The crystals belong to the monoclinic prismatic class and the $a\{100\}$, $c\{001\}$ and $r\{101\}$ faces are the predominant ones. The axial ratio determined by crystallographers is

$a : b : c :: 3.7941 : 1 : 1.1807$, $\beta = 105^\circ 48'$ (Groth, "Chemische Krystallographie", V, p. 34).

* Thianthrene was kindly prepared for our use by Prof. P. C. Guha of the Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore, to whom our best thanks are due.

*Rotation photograph of thianthrene*Plate IV.
a—axis.Plate II.
b—axis.Plate III.
c—axis.

Rotation photograph of diphenyl disulphide

Plate IV.
a-axis.

Plate V.
b-axis.

Plate VI
c-axis.

Photographs.—The rotation photographs about a , b , and c -axis (Plates I, II, III) and several oscillation photographs at suitable intervals about each of the three axes, were taken. The dimensions of the unit cell are

$$a = 23.3 \text{ \AA}, \quad b = 6.14 \text{ \AA}, \quad c = 14.52 \text{ \AA}, \quad \beta = 105^\circ 51',$$

and the axial ratio is

$$a : b : c :: 3.793 : 1 : (2 \times 1.182)$$

which agrees with Groth's except that c/b is doubled. The angle β was directly measured from a number of crystals on all of which the (001) and the (100) faces were very well developed, and was found to be ($\beta = 105^\circ 51'$) the same as given by Groth.

The spots appearing on various oscillation photographs were indexed by the use of Bernal's chart. Tables I and II give the list of planes identified together with an approximate idea of their intensity for which the usual notations have been used.

TABLE I.

Axial planes.	Prism planes.			
	(hol)	(h \bar{o} l)	(okl)	(hko)
002 v.s.	202 s.	202 m.s.	011 v.s.	210 s.
004 s.	204 m.	204 w.	013 s.	220 m.s.
006 m.s.	205 w.	—	014 s.	230 w.m.
008 m.	206 w.	206 w.	015 m.s.	320 m.
020 w.m.	207 v.w.	—	016 w.m.	330 m.
400 v.s.	—	401 m.s.	022 w.m.	410 w.m.
800 w.	402 s.	—	023 w.m.	430 w.m.
(10)00 w.m.	404 w.m.	404 m.	024 w.m.	510 m.s.
(12)00 w.	406 m.	406 w.m.	025 w.	520 w.m.
	601 w.	601 s.	026 w.	530 w.m.

TABLE I. (contd.).

Axial planes.	Prism		Planes.	
	(h0l)	(h0 \bar{l})	(okl)	(hko)
602 w.	602 w.m.	602 \bar{w} .m.	031 w.m.	610 s.
604 w.	604 m.s.	604 \bar{m} .s.	032 w.m.	620 w.m.
605 w.m.	—	—	033 m.s.	720 w.
606 w.m.	—	—	034 m.	730 w.m.
—	—	801 w.	—	810 w.m.
802 w.m.	—	802 w.m.	—	820 w.m.
804 w.m.	—	804 w.m.	—	910 w.m.
—	—	806 w.m.	—	(10)10 w.m.
—	—	807 w.	—	(10)20 w.
—	—	808 w.m.	—	—
(10)02 w.m.	—	(10)02 w.	—	—
—	—	(10)04 w.	—	—
—	—	(10)05 v.w.	—	—
—	—	(10)06 m.s.	—	—
—	—	(12)04 w.	—	—

TABLE II.

General planes.

111 s.	11 $\bar{1}$ v.s.	215 w.	21 $\bar{5}$ w.m.	—	324 w.m.
113 s.	11 $\bar{3}$ s.	216 w.	21 $\bar{6}$ w.	325 w.m.	32 $\bar{5}$ w.m.
—	114 w.	—	217 m.	331 w.m.	33 $\bar{1}$ w.
115 m.s.	11 $\bar{5}$ m.s.	221 s.	22 $\bar{1}$ m.s.	332 w.	33 $\bar{2}$ w.m.
116 w.m.	11 $\bar{6}$ w.m.	222 m.s.	22 $\bar{2}$ m.	—	33 $\bar{3}$ m.

TABLE II. (contd.).

122w.m.	122w.m.	226w.	—	412s.	412s.
123w.m.	123w.	227v.w.	—	413w.	—
124w.m.	124w.	231m.	231w.m.	414w.	414w.
125w.	125w.	232w.	232w.	—	415w.
126w.	126w.	233w.m.	233w.m.	416w.m.	416w.
127v.w.	—	234m.	234m.s.	—	418w.m.
131w.m.	131w.m.	311s.	311m.s.	421m.s.	—
132w.m.	132w.m.	312w.	—	422m.s.	422m.h.
133m.	133w.m.	313w.	313w.m.	—	423w.m.
134m.	134m.	315w.m.	315w.m.	424w.m.	424w.m.
212v.s.	212s.	317w.m.	317m.	425w.m.	425w.m.
213s.	213s.	—	322m.	431w.m.	431w.m.
214m.s.	214m.s.	323m.	323m.s.	432w.	—
—	433w.	—	618v.w.	—	821v.w.
434m.s.	434m.	621w.m.	—	822w.	822w.
511s.	511v.s.	622w.m.	622w.m.	—	825w.m.
512m.	—	623w.	—	—	826w.m.
513w.m.	513w.m.	625m.s.	625m.	911m.s.	911m.s.
515m.	515m.s.	626w.	626w.m.	912w.m.	912m.
—	517m.	631w.m.	631w.m.	913m.	913m.
521w.m.	521m.	633w.	633w.m.	—	915w.
522w.m.	522m.	711w.m.	711w.m.	921w.	921w.m.
523m.	523m.	713w.m.	713w.m.	—	922w.m.
525w.m.	525m.	715w.m.	715w.m.	925w.m.	925m.
—	526m.	—	717w.m.	—	(10) 11w.m.
531m.	—	721w.m.	721w.m.	(10) 12w.m.	(10) 12w.
—	532w.m.	722w.	722w.m.	—	(10) 14w.m.
533w.m.	—	723m.	723m.s.	(10) 22w.m.	(10) 22w.
534w.m.	534m.	725m.	725m.	—	(10) 23w.
612s.	612m.s.	—	726w.	(10) 24w.	(10) 24w.m.
614w.m.	614 v.w.	811w.m.	811m.s.	—	(10) 26w.

TABLE II. (contd.).

117m.s.	$\bar{1}\bar{1}\bar{7}$ w.m.	224w.m.	$2\bar{2}\bar{4}$ w.	—	$3\bar{3}\bar{4}$ w
121v.s.	121s.	—	$2\bar{2}\bar{5}$ v.w.	326v.w.	—
615w.m.	—	812w.m.	$8\bar{1}\bar{2}$ w.m.	(11)11w.m.	(11)11w.
616v.w.	$6\bar{1}\bar{6}$ w.m.	—	$8\bar{1}\bar{3}$ m.	—	(11)11w.
—	$6\bar{1}\bar{7}$ w.m.	—	$8\bar{1}\bar{5}$ w.m.	—	(11)15w.m.
—	(11)15v.w.	—	(11)24w.	—	(12)13w.
(11)21w.	—	—	(11)25w.m.	—	(12)14w.
—	(11)22w.	—	(12)11w.m.	—	(12)13w.m.
—	(11)23w.	—	(12)12w.	—	—

The above tables show that (hol) planes are halved when h is odd and (000) is also halved. These halvings correspond to the space group C_{2h}^2 ($P2_1/n$) with Γ_m Bravais lattice (Astbury and Yardly, *Phil. Trans.*, 1924, **A** 224, 230). The maximum number of asymmetric units required to complete the symmetry of this group is four. The number of molecules (mol. wt. 216) calculated from the observed data is eight (accurately 8.04).

The chemical molecule of thianthrene is represented as in (I). This representation resembles that of anthracene (II) in all respects excepting that the two carbon atoms in positions 9 and 10 in (II) are replaced by S atoms.

(I)

(II)

In the case of anthracene which also belongs to the space group C_{2h}^2 , Bragg (*Proc. Phys. Soc.*, 1922, **34**, 33) has found that the calculated number of molecules per unit cell is only two, thus showing that the molecules are centro-symmetrical. In thianthrene, however, the results show that the number of molecules is double the number required by the unit cell. Such a result can only be explained by the assumption that two chemical mole-

cules of thianthrene polymerise* to form an asymmetric unit of the elementary cell. The result appears surprising indeed looking to the high symmetry apparently exhibited by the chemical representation of the molecule. Cases of polymerisation taking place in the crystal unit, though rare, have been discovered by various workers from the results of X-ray analysis. Amongst the earliest examples, mention may be made of the results on phenylenediamines studied by Caspari (*Phil. Mag.*, 1927, **4**, 1276). Triphenylmethane studied by Prasad, deSousa and Jagdish (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1936, **5**, 109) is another example of a similar nature. K. Banerjee has recently reported more such examples both in organic and inorganic compounds (*Proc. Indian Science Congress*, 1937).

Diphenyl Disulphide.

Eastman and Kodak's diphenyl disulphide was purified by recrystallisation from amyl acetate. The pure substance melted at 61° and the specific gravity was found to be 1.339. Well developed crystals were obtained by slow evaporation of a solution of the substance in acetone. The following table gives the interfacial angles.

TABLE III.

Interfacial angles of diphenyl disulphide.

Faces.	Groth's values		Authors' values	
	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.
(110) : (1 $\bar{1}$ 0)	68° 36'	—	68° 42'	68° 40'
(210) : (2 $\bar{1}$ 0)	—	+37° 40'	37° 43'	—
(230) : (010)	44° 21'	†44 40'	44° 17'	—
(101) : (100)	—	+53° 50'	55° 9'	—
(101) : (210)	56° 3'	55° 47'	57° 16½'	—
(101) : (1 $\bar{0}$ 1)	72° 20'	—	69° 42'	70° 10'
(011) : (010)	63° 30'	64° 8'	64° 33'	—
(011) : (0 $\bar{1}$ 1)	53° 0'	—	50° 54'	52° 0'

* It may be mentioned here that cases of polymerisation known in organic chemistry are fundamentally different from the one dealt with here. For example, acetaldehyde (CH₃CHO) polymerises to give paraldehyde, (CH₃CHO)₃, which has chemical and physical properties entirely different from the parent substance.

† The plane (230) given here is (340) mentioned by Groth (*loc. cit.*). This seems to be a misprint or an error.

The crystals belong to the orthorhombic system and the axial ratio is

$$a : b : c = 0.6821 : 1 : 0.4987 \text{ (Groth, } loc. cit., p. 33).$$

Photographs.—The rotation photographs taken about the three crystallographic axes (Plates IV, V and VI) give the following dimensions of the unit cell

$$a = 8.1\text{\AA}, \quad b = 23.70\text{\AA} \quad c = 5.64\text{\AA}$$

and the axial ratio is

$$a : b : c = 0.3418 : 1 : 0.2380.$$

It will be seen that the *b*-axis is doubled in this case (*cf.* Groth, *loc. cit.*). The ratio *b* : *c* obtained by the authors is slightly lower than that expected from Groth's value. However, Table III shows that the observed angles are in better agreement with those calculated from author's ratio. Tables IV and V give the list of planes identified on the oscillation photographs about the three crystallographic axes.

TABLE IV.

Axial planes.	Prism planes.		
	(okl).	(hol).	(hko).
002 m.	011 m.s.	101 m.s.	110 v.s.
020 m.s.	012 m.	102 m.	120 m.
040 w.m.	021 s.	201 m.s.	130 m.
060 v.s.	023 w.	202 m.s.	140 m.
080 m.s.	031 s.	301 m.	150 w.
0(12)0 m.	032 w.m..	302 v.w.	160 m.
200 s.	041 m.	401 w.	170 m.
400 m.	042 w.	...	180 v.w.
...	043 w.	...	190 m.
...	051 m.	...	1(10)0 w.
...	052 w.m.	...	1(11)0 w.m.
...	061 m.	...	1(12)0 w.m.
...	062 w.m.	...	210 m.
...	063 w.	...	220 m.s.
...	071 m.	...	230 m.
...	072 w.m.	...	240 m.
...	081 m.	...	250 v.w.
...	091 w.m.	...	260 m.
...	092 v.w.	...	270 w.
...	0(10)1 w.	...	280 w.
...	0(11)1 w.
...	0(12)1 w.

TABLE V.

General planes.

111 s.	171 m.	242 w.	332 w.m.
112 m.s.	172 w.m.	251 m.	341 w.
113 w.m.	181 m.	252 w.m.	342 w.m.
121 m.s.	182 w.m.	261 m.	351 w.
122 w.	191 w.m.	262 w.	352 w.
123 w.	192 w.	271 w.m.	361 m.
131 m.	1(10)1 w.	281 w.m.	362 w.
132 w.m.	1(10)2 w.m.	291 w.	371 w.
133 w.	1(11)1 w.	292 v.w.	381 w.
141 w.m.	1(12)1 w.m.	2(10)1 v.w.	391 v.w.
142 m.s.	211 m.s.	2(11)1 w.m.	411 w.
143 w.	212 w.	2(12)1 v.w.	421 w.m.
151 m.s.	221 m.s.	311 m.	431 w.
152 w.p.	222 m.	312 w.	441 w.
153 v.w.	231 m.s.	321 m.	451 w.
161 m.s.	232 m.s.	322 w.m.	461 w.
162 w.	241 w.	331 m.s.	...

From the above list of planes, it will be seen that planes (hoo), (oko), or (ool) are halved when h, k or l are, respectively, odd. The crystals, therefore, belong to the rhombic bisphenoidal class and to the space group Q^4 with Γ_0 Bravais lattice. The number of molecules calculated from the dimensions of the cell and specific gravity of crystals is four (accurately 4.005) which is the same as the maximum number of asymmetric units required to complete the symmetry of the space group Q^4 . Thus it would seem that the molecules are asymmetric.

The chemical molecule of diphenyl disulphide is represented as in (III). From this representation the molecule appears to be similar to those of dibenzyl series (IV—VI).

(III) Diphenyl disulphide.

(IV) Dibenzyl.

(V) Stilbene

(VI) Azobenzene.

Now, in the case of dibenzyl, Dbar (*loc. cit.*) has shown that the number of molecules is half the number of asymmetric units required by the space group. This is indicative of a centre of symmetry in dibenzyl. In the case of stilbene and azobenzene also Robertson, Prasad and Woodward (*loc. cit.*) have shown that the molecules are centro-symmetrical although the calculated number of molecules is the same as the number required to complete the symmetry of the cell.

From this it appears that the possibility of molecules of diphenyl disulphide possessing a centre of symmetry is not entirely to be excluded.